

Peyton Reed, dir. *Ant-Man and the Wasp: Quantumania* (Marvel Studios, 2023)

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After *Avengers: Endgame* (2019), the Marvel Cinematic Universe has been preoccupied with the Multiverse and the control of time. *Quantumania* is both the sequel to *Ant-Man and the Wasp* (2018) and the first entry in Phase 5 of the MCU. The film initiates the plot-lines of subsequent Marvel productions already confirmed including *Loki* (season 2) and the forthcoming *Avengers: The Kang Dynasty*.

Having already rescued the original Wasp, Janet van Dyne (Michelle Pfeiffer), from the Quantum Realm in the previous film, Scott Lang/Ant-Man (Paul Rudd), his daughter Cassie (Kathryn Newton), his girlfriend Hope van Dyne/The Wasp (Evangeline Lilly), and her parents Janet and Hank Pym (Michael Douglas) are all accidentally transported back into the Realm. There they have to confront the despotic ruler, Kang the Conqueror (Jonathan Majors), the MCU's latest super-villain. One of the main questions posed by the film is that of empire and colonialism since Kang, who can travel throughout time and space, has used his power to conquer the entire population of the Quantum Realm. Although the original comic-book villain is blue-skinned, Marvel have opted not to portray Kang like other multi-coloured characters, such as Thanos (Josh Brolin) and Gamora (Zoe Saldana), but as an explicitly black antagonist. Kang's empire suggests an immediate contrast to the Afrofuturist utopia of Wakanda from the *Black Panther* films. The movie sidesteps, though, issues of race and racism to focus on more quintessential Marvel themes of power and responsibility. Kang uses his time-travelling ability irresponsibly in order to acquire dominion over others. First seen in season one of *Loki* (2021) as 'He Who Remains', Kang is exiled outside time and space by his variants in other timelines, which fuels his desire to control and destroy the Multiverse. Yet, as he admits, 'I don't live in a straight line. And with time, it's hard not to skip to the end', a sentiment which, coupled to Majors's sensitive performance in an otherwise hectic narrative, adds tragic pathos to Kang's characterisation.

The other fundamental Marvel theme, in common with those of power and responsibility, is resilience, which the film portrays as the ability to adapt to adversity. It is this which gives the characters the strength, through collaboration and cooperation, to defeat Kang. There is a potential downside to this representation